

FAIR RDM kompetencematrix

“Fostering FAIR Data Practices in Europe”-projektet FAIRsFAIR har produceret en række rapporter og materialer omkring FAIR datapraksis. Arbejdsgruppe D anbefaler at bruge *FAIR Competence Framework for Higher Education (FAIR4HE)*: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4562088> & <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5665492> for at beskrive kompetencerne og læringsmål inden for FAIR RDM.

Den vedhæftede oversigt over FAIR RDM-kompetencer på hhv. Bachelor-, Master- og PhD-niveau er baseret på Appendix E fra Engelhardt et al. (2022). Arbejdsgruppen har tilføjet en ekstra kolonne med kompetenceønsker fra aftagere i det private erhvervsliv, men det skal betragtes som en første sondering.

Referencer

Demchenko, Y., Stoy, L., Engelhardt, C. & Gaillard, V. (2021). *D7.3 FAIR Competence Framework for Higher Education (Data Stewardship Professional Competence Framework)* (1.0). Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5361917> (= FAIR4HE)

Engelhardt, C., Biernacka, K. et al. (2022). *D7.4 How to be FAIR with your data. A teaching and training handbook for higher education institutions* (V1.2.1) Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6674301>

Content/topic [from FAIR Competences BOK], based on EDISON Data Science Framework	basic learning outcomes	intermediate learning outcomes (include and build on basic learning outcomes)	advanced learning outcomes (include and build on intermediate learning outcomes)	Bachelor (FAIRsFAIR)	Master (FAIRsFAIR)	PhD (FAIRsFAIR)	Aftagere i det private erhvervsliv (AG-D)	Entry-Level Content?
General principles and concepts in data management – overview	1. Can define Research Data Management (RDM) and can describe its relevance and benefits.	2. Can describe RDM measures to be taken (including explaining why) at different stages of the research process.	3. Can practically apply theoretical knowledge about proper RDM measures to be taken at different stages to their own research process/project.	basic	intermediate	advanced	B	Yes
Overview of data types, data type registries and data formats	1. Can describe what types of data exist (Knowledge). 2. Can explain what data type registries are (Knowledge). 3. Can identify data formats (Knowledge). 4. Can search and find data formats in registries.	5. Can determine proper data types for a resource (Analyse). 6. Can use a data type registry (Apply). 7. Can use proper data formats to express resources (Apply).		basic	basic	intermediate	B	Yes
Metadata, metadata formats, metadata standards and metadata registries	1. Can describe types of metadata. 2. Can recognise metadata formats. 3. Can identify metadata standards. 4. Can use metadata standards to describe resources. 5. Can explain what metadata registries are. 6. Can search and find data and metadata standards in registries.	7. Can articulate metadata of different types to describe a resource. 8. Can write metadata in a relevant format. 9. Can appraise the usefulness of metadata standards to describe a resource. 10. Can search metadata registries to find resources.	11. Can design rich metadata to describe a resource. 12. Can use proper metadata formats and models to express these metadata. 13. Can deposit metadata in a repository.	basic	intermediate	advanced	B	Yes
Open Research, Open Access, Open Data	1. Can paraphrase the concept of Open Research. 2. Can describe the benefits of Open Research. 3. Can describe Open Access and Open Data as areas of Open Research.	4. Can recognise if a publication is open access. 5. Can discover platforms for Open Access/Open Data. 6. Can articulate what is required to make research outputs open. 7. Can contrast FAIR and Open.	8. Can plan publication of Open Access publications and FAIR data.	basic	intermediate	advanced		Yes
Metadata management, registries and publication	1. Can explain aspects of metadata management and the publication process in metadata registries.	2. Can perform basic steps related to metadata management. 3. Can execute steps in metadata publication.	4. Can select appropriate metadata formats and a metadata registry appropriate for the subject domain of a research project.	basic	basic	intermediate		No
Persistent Identifiers (PID), Open Researcher and Contributor ID (ORCID), Research Organization Registry (ROR)	1. Can recognise PIDs and explain the different use cases for PIDs. 2. Can explain the importance of PIDs for FAIR data. 3. Can use PIDs to access data or other resources.	4. Can apply PIDs to their own research outputs. 5. Can use PIDs to collaborate with others.		basic	basic	intermediate	B	Yes
FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles in data management	1. Can paraphrase the FAIR principles. 2. Can explain why the FAIR principles were developed. 3. Can recognise the relationship between FAIR, RDM and Open.	4. Can plan for FAIR research outputs. 5. Can write and develop a research data management plan. 6. Can apply the principles to their own work. 7. Can evaluate the FAIRness of their own work or the work of others.		basic	basic	intermediate	I	Yes
FAIR metadata management and tools for FAIR metadata management	1. Can name aspects related to FAIR metadata management. 2. Can give an example of tools for FAIR metadata management.	3. Can describe aspects of metadata management to comply with FAIR. 4. Can work with one of the FAIR metadata management tools.	5. Is able to support FAIR metadata management for the selected subject domain. 6. Can assess and select tools for FAIR metadata management.	basic	intermediate	advanced		No
Databases and database management systems, data modelling	1. Can explain what a database is, including common database terminology. 2. Can explain and list some of the advantages and disadvantages of using databases. 3. Can distinguish between databases and spreadsheets. 4. Can recall basic concept of data modelling.	5. Can identify basic database classifications and discuss their differences. 6. Can recall the most common database models and discuss their usage. 7. Understands how a relational database is designed, created, used, and maintained. 8. Is able to build and assess data-based models.		basic	basic	basic	B	No
Data structures	1. Understands and can restate the fundamentals of basic data structures. 2. Is able to implement and apply data structures.	3. Is able to describe the usage of various data structures algorithms. 4. Is able to explain and summarise the advantages and disadvantages of various data structures implementations.	5. Is able to analyse the performance characteristics of algorithms using mathematical and measurement techniques. 6. Is able to design and apply appropriate data structures for solving computing problems.	basic	basic	basic		No
Master data management, data dictionaries	1. Can develop a data management plan for their own work. 2. Can identify different types of data documentation. 3. Can explain the purpose of the documentation. 4. Can use existing documentation.	5. Can modify existing documentation. 6. Can evaluate and prioritise data management activities.		basic	basic	intermediate		Yes
FAIR data management requirements and compliance	1. Can name the main stakeholders or parties that potentially mandate FAIR compliance and data management measures. 2. Can list FAIR data management requirements.	3. Can identify the FAIR and RDM requirements that are relevant for the own research context. 4. Can explain where to get support with regard to RDM and the FAIR principles. 5. Can plan proper measures for RDM and making data FAIR (with support if necessary). 6. Can apply proper measures for RDM and making data FAIR (with support if necessary).	7. Can plan proper measures for RDM and making data FAIR (without support). 8. Can apply proper measures for RDM and making data FAIR (without support).	irrelevant	basic	intermediate		No
Data management, including reference and master data	1. Can define reference and master data. 2. Understands the critical roles reference and master data play in data management.	3. Can describe different Master Data Management (MDM) architectures and their suitability for different needs.	4. Is able to design a Data Governance Framework and to manage master and reference data.	irrelevant	basic	basic		No
Data storage and operations	1. Can identify different options for data storage and their operational aspects. 2. Can state different types and functions of storage systems.	3. Can specify and explain requirements regarding data storage for specific data or organisational processes.	4. Can compare different storage options. 5. Can select and justify a data storage solution for a project or organisation.	basic	intermediate	advanced		No
Data infrastructure, data registries and data factories	1. Can list existing infrastructure elements and services required to support consistent data management and handling.	2. Can specify and explain requirements with regard to the data infrastructure and its components for specific data or organisational data.	3. Can compare different infrastructure solutions. 4. Can select and justify a data storage solutions for a project or organisation. 5. Understands the role and functions of the data factories.	basic	basic	intermediate		No

Data security and protection	1. Can define different levels of data security (user, folder, files). 2. Can explain different ways of data protection (physical, encryption etc.).	3. Can use different levels of security for their own work. 4. Can apply data protection methods like password protection and encoding. 5. Does share and collaborate in a secure way.		basic	basic	intermediate	B	Yes
Data backup	1. Can describe what a backup is and tell reasons for backup creation. 2. Can explain the 3-2-1 rule and apply it to their own files. 3. Can identify institutional backup solutions.	4. Can explain institutional backup solutions and apply them to own files.	5. Can analyse and evaluate backup. 6. Can solve backup problems independently or with further assistance from support personnel.	basic	intermediate	advanced		Yes
Personal data protection, GDPR compliance	1. Can explain reasons for data protection. 2. Knows basic rules and legal regulations for sensitive data (e.g. GDPR). 3. Knows how to comply with these rules and laws.	4. Can analyse compliance to legal regulations for sensitive data. 5. Can apply mechanisms to protect data appropriately.		basic	basic	intermediate (depending on discipline)	B	Yes
Data anonymisation/pseudonymisation	1. Can describe directly identifying attributes and detect them in data. 2. Can explain the difference between anonymisation and pseudonymisation.	3. Can anonymise/pseudonymise data by stripping identifying attributes.		basic	intermediate (depending on discipline)	intermediate (depending on discipline)		No
Data management planning, FAIR data management and compliance	1. Can describe what a data management plan (DMP) is. 2. Can explain why data management planning is a step towards FAIR.	3. Can tell which areas should be covered in a DMP. 4. Can sketch a DMP for their own research project.	5. Can develop a detailed DMP according to funder requirements and engage with relevant university instances/authorities. 6. Can collaborate on a DMP and modify the plan during the project progress ("living document"). 7. Can apply principles to protect personal sensitive data and develop Data Protection Impact Assessment, if required. (depending on discipline)	basic	basic	intermediate		Yes
Data integration and interoperability, data preparation and data cleaning	1. Can explain aspects related to data interoperability and integration. 2. Can explain aspects of data preparation and cleaning.	3. Can perform basic tasks in data interoperability and integration. 4. Can perform basic tasks in data preparation and cleaning.	5. Can select best solutions/standards for data interoperability. 6. Can select appropriate tools and methods for data integration. 7. Can select appropriate methods and tools for data preparation and cleaning.	basic	intermediate	advanced	B	No
Data interoperability and metadata management	1. Can explain aspects of interoperability (Knowledge). 2. Can relate metadata management to interoperability (Understand).	3. Can name roles and structures in data governance and knows how they work together. 4. Can relate metadata management to interoperability (Apply).		basic	basic	intermediate	B	Yes (basic concept)
Organisational roles in data governance, data stewardship	1. Can define data governance and name its components. 2. Can name different roles involved in data governance.	3. Can name roles and structures in data governance and knows how they work together. 4. Can recall goals and added value of data governance.	5. Can develop strategies to successfully embed data governance in an organisation.	basic	basic	intermediate		No
Data provenance, data lineage	1. Can illustrate with an example what data provenance/data lineage means.	2. Can transfer how data provenance/data lineage plays a role in their own research project. 3. Can apply data provenance good practices to their own data and ensure that an unbroken data lineage is established for their work.	4. Can use tools for data provenance management.	basic	basic	intermediate	I	Yes
Responsible data use, data privacy, ethical principles, IPR and legal issues	1. Can summarise and explain ethical principles and responsible data use (e.g. CARE, indigenous data). 2. Can describe legal issues around data use and management (e.g. licences, patents, policies, contracts etc.).	3. Can analyse if ethical principles or legal issues play a role in their own work.	4. Can detect ethical or legal issues and solve them together with ethical and legal experts like e.g., ethics committee, data protection officers or lawyers from the institution.	basic	intermediate	advanced	I	Yes
Data quality management, best practices and frameworks, data quality metrics	1. Can summarise best practices ensuring data quality.	2. Can describe how to recognise quality data.	3. Can use best practices and frameworks on their own data to ensure their quality.	basic	intermediate	advanced	B	Yes (basic concept)
Data protection policies (including personal data), data access policies, GDPR compliance	1. Can state general requirements on data protection and access control. 2. Can give examples of policies related to data protection and access control. 3. Can list the main aspects related to the GDPR.	4. Can explain general requirements on data protection and access control. 5. Can explain content and use of policies related to data protection and access control. 6. Can explain what are the main aspects related to GDPR in organisational data management.	7. Can write specific policies related to data protection and access. 8. Can analyse compliance to GDPR in organisational data management.	basic	intermediate	advanced	B	No
Trusted data repositories and certification	1. Can explain what a trusted data repository is and how to find it (re3data.org and FAIRsharing). 2. Can compare different certifications for data repositories (e.g. CoreTrustSeal, CLARIN certification).	3. Can discover trusted repositories and identify those that are certified.	4. Can use a trusted repository to share research output.	basic	basic	intermediate		Yes (basic concept)
Data discovery (published data), data selection and use in research	1. Can explain the importance of data discovery and reuse.	2. Can discover published datasets in their discipline. 3. Can cite data.	4. Can develop a strategy to search for data. 5. Can articulate criteria for data selection. 6. Can extract datasets and build their own work on them.	basic	intermediate	advanced	B	Yes (basic concept)
Research data lifecycle	1. Can explain the steps of the research data lifecycle. 2. Can compare different lifecycle models.	3. Can apply the research data lifecycle to their own work.		basic	basic	intermediate		Yes
Ontologies, controlled vocabularies	1. Can explain the role of ontologies and vocabularies (Knowledge). 2. Can recognise the use of ontologies and vocabularies (Knowledge). 3. Can identify a few domain-relevant ontologies (Knowledge). 4. Can search and find terminologies in registries.	5. Can use ontologies to describe resources (Apply).	6. Can use ontologies for search and analysis (Apply).	basic	intermediate	advanced		Yes